

Impact of Deforestation, High Temperature & Urbanization on Dengue Fever Transmission in Dhaka City

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Introduction

Dengue is a vector-borne illness that spreads quickly, and a number of environmental conditions might affect how the disease spreads. The combination of high temperatures, deforestation, and fast urbanization in metropolitan areas such as Dhaka City facilitates the growth of *Aedes* mosquitoes, which are the main carriers of the dengue virus.

Objective

The objective of this research is to assess the relationship between high temperatures, deforestation, urbanization, and the incidence of dengue fever in Dhaka

Methodology

Dengue Epidemic

OBJECT ID	Class Name	Count (2019)
1	Water Land	2343
2	Bare Land	23915
3	Built-up Area	209682
4	Forest Land	871
5	Vegetation Land	95621

OBJECT ID	Class Name	Count (2023)
1	Water Land	1588
2	Bare Land	8747
3	Built-up Area	231600
4	Forest Land	488
5	Vegetation Land	90009

Preliminary Result

Preliminary investigations link Dhaka City dengue fever cases to deforestation, urbanization, and high temperatures. Along with this, we are keeping our fingers crossed that the dengue outbreak that has hit Dhaka is associated with certain areas of urbanization.

Conclusion

The results will add to the expanding body of research on urban vector-borne illness environmental factors, helping design effective public health policies and interventions to minimize dengue outbreaks in rapidly urbanizing locations